

¿CÓMO QUE BILINGÜE? INFLUENCE OF HOME LANGUAGE ON MAZE USE IN
SPANISH-ENGLISH BILINGUAL COLLEGE STUDENTS IN ORANGE COUNTY

by

Rebeca De La Cruz

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6511-8008

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6654098

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2022

Approved by:

Date:

5/12/2022

Rahul Chakraborty, Ph.D., CCC-SLP, Department of
Communication Sciences and Disorders

5/31/2022

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Director

University Honors Program

ABSTRACT

Despite the legal protections of Title VII of the Civil Rights Act, discrimination of bilingual individuals on the basis of their perceived language proficiency and accent continues to be a prevalent and largely unexplored issue. With this project, I seek to analyze one aspect of the complex linguistic reality of Spanish (L1)-English (L2) bilingualism among college-aged students in Orange County through the lens of maze, or normal disfluencies. This study will focus on characteristics of English L2 speech produced by Spanish L1 speakers.

The goal of this study is to examine how the home language of Spanish-English (SE) bilinguals influences their English L2 production skills. These skills are indexed through mazing behaviors. I hypothesize that the frequency and type of mazes will vary directly as a function of participants' home language, with L1-only home language users demonstrating a greater quantity and variety of mazes in English.

These findings could be used as a basis for further studies regarding specific areas to target in acquiring more native-like speech qualities in a speaker's L2. They may also inform education and language professionals of the unique and diverse language profiles of their bilingual students, and the necessity of not approaching their education in a monolithic manner.

Keywords: bilingualism, mazes, Spanish-English bilingualism, home language

INTRODUCTION

In the field of linguistics, mazes are defined as non-disordered disfluencies found in the flow of speech and can include pauses, repetitions, revisions, and/or connectors (Loban, 1976). Examples of pauses include the use of empty space or filler words such as “um” (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006). Repetitions include the reduplication of a sound, partial word, whole word, or phrase. Revisions may be of a specific sound, a word, or the grammatical structure of an utterance. Connectors are defined as the repetitive use of conjunctions or time markers at the beginning of utterances.

During the initial stages of research on linguistic mazes, they were first thought to be a clinical indicator of processing difficulties due to a language disorder, with greater maze use generally signaling a language disorder. Leadolm and Miller (1994) found that, as compared to monolingual children from an English-speaking background with typically developing language, children with Language Impairment produce a higher frequency of mazes and longer mazes—for instance, mazing over three to four words (Leadolm and Miller, 1995). Thus, linguistic proficiency is known to influence maze use patterns in monolingual speakers. However, later studies found that both children and adults with typically developing language also use mazes. Typically developing children have been shown to demonstrate increased maze use when formulating longer and more complex utterances (Eckert, 1990). Additionally, adult speakers with superior language skills have been shown to produce mazes as well (Nippold, 2007).

More recent studies by Chakraborty, Domsch, and Gonzales characterize mazes as a speaker’s attempt to control the context or ambiguity of their communicative content, the syntactic and phonological patterns, and the synergy between the speaker’s intention and

production (Chakraborty et al., 2017). There is evidence that mazes are overt manifestations of cognitive-linguistic demands, such as in working through language-specific tasks and simultaneous self-monitoring and covert repair. Because of their nature, they can provide a unique insight into a speaker's underlying phonological, morphological, syntactic, semantic, and neurophysiological processes.

Although not to the degree originally prescribed, there still exists today a debate as to whether mazes should be utilized as a clinical marker of disordered speech or language. Particularly within the school setting, speech-language pathologists analyze maze use and frequency as part of the language sample analysis process when conducting an assessment for children with suspected speech or language disorders (SALT).

This study seeks to objectively contribute evidence to this argument. The findings will be discussed at the end of this paper.

Of particular interest is the role of maze use among bilingual individuals. As has been found in more recent studies, maze use has been identified as a characteristic of language that more commonly occurs in bilingual speech production versus in monolingual speech production (Valles, 2016). This is because, at least in children, individuals are more likely to make expressive errors of language production in their least dominant language (Ribot & Hoff, 2014). This phenomenon makes sense because a speaker who utilizes a language less frequently is more likely to produce errors in that language. Unfortunately, this discovery came decades too late for the disproportionate number of bilingual clients who, thanks to historical preconceptions of mazes as clinical indicators of a language disorder, were misdiagnosed as having a language disorder when they merely exhibited a language difference. This is but one example in a long history of systemic discrimination of individuals on the basis of their language, despite the presence of legal protections to the

contrary (Legal Aid Society; Matsuda, 1991; Leonard, 2004; Leonard, 2007). This highlights the importance of researching linguistic mazes: to better inform clinical, evidence-based practice that is culturally and linguistically appropriate. A deeper, more nuanced understanding of the underlying properties of maze will allow for a more informed clinical implementation.

Past studies suggest that adult sequential bilingual speakers differ in their use of mazes in their L2, depending on their L1 background (Chakraborty et al., 2011). Additionally, a previous study with Bengali bilinguals demonstrated a difference only in one type of maze, Empty Pauses (EP), with early bilinguals demonstrating less EP as compared to late bilinguals (Chakraborty, Domsch, & Gonzales, 2011). A recent study by Chakraborty, Kim, Trevino, De La Cruz, and Moss found that the L1 background of early sequential bilingual adults variably influences the number and type of mazes produced (particularly pauses and connectors) in a narrative task (Chakraborty et al., 2021). The fact that the nature of language exposure appeared to have influenced the nature and type of maze productions suggests that there is a difference between surface level language behaviors and deeper, nuanced language behaviors. These two studies constitute among the only published studies related to maze use among adult bilingual speakers.

Most existing studies exploring the role of mazing between monolingual and bilingual groups explore the phenomenon in children (Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006; Guo, Tomblin, and Samelson, 2008; Byrd, Bedore, and Ramos, 2015; Valles, 2016; Taliencich-Klinger and Bedore, 2019). Apart from preliminary studies focusing on the age of L2 exposure (Chakraborty et al., 2017; Chakraborty et al., 2021) and a neurolinguistic study comparing performance between three types of bilingual speakers—heritage language

speakers, native speakers, and nonnative speakers (Enríquez, 2020)—the nature of maze behaviors has remained largely unexplored in adults.

There are currently no published studies exploring the role of an adult bilingual speaker's home language on their L2 mazing performance. Due to the inherent diversity of the bilingual experience, particularly among SE bilinguals in Orange County, California (De La Cruz y Finley, 2021), it is important to keep in mind the role that differentiates one bilingual's experience from that of another bilingual. One such differentiator could include a speaker's home language. While some bilinguals solely use their native language in the home setting, others may use their native language in conjunction with their second language. Home language could be a useful variable because it implies that the speaker uses this language at least somewhat consistently with a consistent group of people. Additionally, an analysis focusing on home language would provide a unique insight into the degree which linguistic assimilation to the dominant language and culture plays within this population of Spanish-English bilinguals in Orange County.

The Present Study

The goal of this project is to see whether—and if so, how a bilingual speaker's home language affects their linguistic performance in their second language. For the purposes of this study, the home language groups constitute 1) those who use Spanish only at home and 2) those who use both Spanish and English at home. All participants are Spanish-English bilinguals, meaning that their first language (L1) is Spanish, and their second language (L2) is English.

The hypothesis, based on previous research, is that individuals who solely use their L1 at home will demonstrate more frequent and diverse types of mazes in their L2

(English) speech production. This study is significant because it seeks to address the gap in literature regarding the impact of home language on L2 production. It will also contribute to the existing literature positing the use of mazes not as straightforward indicators of language disorders, but rather as a complex phenomenon that are simply a piece of a multifaceted diagnosing process.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

As part of a larger study, fourteen Spanish (L1)-English (L2) bilingual college students between the ages of 18 and 25 were selectively recruited for this study based on language characteristics (see Appendix I: Promotional Flyer). Participants were recruited from California State University, Fullerton. Prior to participating in the study, interested participants received and submitted a case history survey to gather sociolinguistic data (see Appendix II: Language Case History). The survey addressed the participant's age of arrival to the United States (if they reported they were not born and brought up in the United States); whether English was their primary language; their age of initial exposure to the English language; whether they knew any other languages besides English; how many hours within a day they used their other language(s) in an expressive modality; what language they used to interact with family members; whether they speak a different language at home; and their sex.

Inclusionary criteria. In order to participate in the study, individuals must have self-reported as having a primary language (LA) of English, be at least 18 years of age, and a

bilingual Spanish-English speaker. This information was collected via a screening questionnaire prior to formal recruitment.

Exclusionary criteria. Participants in this study did not have any reported history of speech, language, or hearing impairments. Each of these impairments was ruled out for all participants prior to beginning the study by means of oral motor examination, case history, and hearing screening. The oral motor examination informally and subjectively assessed structure and function of the lips, tongue, oral cavity, velum, and voice. The case history asked the individual to report any history of speech, language, or hearing impairments. Hearing was screened at 500, 1000, 2000, 4000, and 6000 Hz at 25 decibels.

Of the fourteen participants (N = 14), seven reported that they only use Spanish at home (n = 7). These were coded as HLS to indicate “Home Language is Spanish.” The remaining seven reported that they use both Spanish and English at home (n = 7). These were coded as HLSE to indicate “Home Language is Spanish and English.”

All fourteen participants reported that they were born and brought up in the United States. All participants reported a history of normal speech, language, and hearing, and have lived in the same geographic area—Orange County, California.

Stimuli and Procedure

Each participant completed three expressive language tasks. The first task was reading “The Grandfather Passage” by Darley et al. (1975) (see Appendix III: Testing Stimuli). This task is a generic, 132-word reading passage that includes a diverse array of all English phonemes both in isolation and nested within an array of phonotactically improbable clusters (Reilly and Fisher, 2012). It is complex articulatorily, semantically, and syntactically, and has thus been used clinically by speech-language pathologists as an ideal

mode of eliciting speech and reading errors. This stimulus was presented face-down until all recording equipment was set up and the participant was ready to begin. Once the participant was ready, they were instructed to turn over the passage and begin reading out loud. No additional time to read the passage was given ahead of time. The participant was asked to read it as if naturally reading a passage aloud. They were allowed to correct their own mistakes while reading. No feedback was provided during the reading of the passage.

The other two language samples consisted of spontaneous narrative speech, which was gathered using two different Picture Description Tasks (PDT) (see Appendix III: Testing Stimuli). The first stimulus presented was the “Lion and the Rat” stimulus, which entailed a picture sequence based on Aesop’s fable, which is common to English linguistic heritage (Pinkney). In this picture sequence, a lion catches a mouse and decides to release him. The mouse reciprocates in gratitude, with a comparable life-saving gesture towards the lion in the end. The second picture card stimulus was the “Cookie Theft” picture taken from the Boston Diagnostic Aphasia Examination-Third Edition by Goodglass, Kaplan, and Barresi (2001). This picture depicts a domestic scene from Western civilization with people, their attires, the setting, and the actions in the picture.

For the picture description task, the stimulus was presented face-down, and the participant turned it over once they were ready to record. No additional time to see the pictures was given ahead of time. The participant was asked to describe to the examiner what they saw in the picture. Participants were allowed to self-correct any verbal errors. In this task, they were asked to aim to speak for as close to five minutes (about 2.5 minutes per picture task) as they could.

The order of presentation was fixed: “Grandfather Passage”, then “Lion and the Rat”, and then “Cookie Theft.” Participants were asked to describe what they saw in each

picture for approximately two minutes each. Participants sat on a chair with a microphone mounted 10 inches from their mouth. All productions were recorded using an Audio-Technica AT 4033A cardioid condenser microphone onto the software, Avid ProTools, in a sound-treated booth at the California State University, Fullerton Speech and Hearing Clinic.

Analysis

After all audio recordings were completed, complete transcripts for each recording were transcribed using Microsoft Word and the acoustic analysis software, PRAAT. A total of 42 audio files (14 participants x 3 tasks each) were transcribed.

Each transcript was then analyzed for maze use. For the purposes of this project, there were five main maze subtypes that were analyzed: time-dependent measures (i.e., empty pauses and filled pauses); measures for repetitions (sound repetition, part-word repetition, whole-word repetition, and phrase repetition); measures for revisions (phase revisions, lexical revisions, and grammatical revisions); connectors (repetitive use of conjunctions or time markers at the beginning of utterances); and other maze types that were identified but did not fit within the aforementioned categories. In order to standardize the process across all samples, operational definitions were set for each maze type. The operational definitions for the types of mazes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Maze Type Definitions and Examples

MAZE TYPE	DEFINITION	EXAMPLE
Empty Pause (EP)	Silent intervals, two or more seconds in length (Nettelbladt and Hansson, 1999)	The ... (2.05s) frog jumped

Filled Pause (FP)	Non-linguistic vocalization that occurs at the beginning of utterances or between words (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	(Um) the frog jumped
Sound Repetition (SR)	Repeating a previous phoneme of the utterance before carrying on (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	The (f*) frog jumped
Part-Word Repetition (PWR)	Repetition of a group of phonemes (i.e., syllable) part of a word before carrying on (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	The (fr*) frog jumped
Whole-Word Repetition (WWR)	Repetition of a whole word before carrying on (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	The (frog) frog jumped
Phase Repetition (PR)	Repetition of two or more words in either initial, medial, or final position of an utterance before carrying on (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	(The frog) the frog jumped
Phonological Revision (PhonoRev)	Correction of phonological errors (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	The (grog) frog jumped
Lexical Revision (LexRev)	Correction of overt word choice errors; to add or delete lexical information (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	(My) the frog jumped
Grammatical Revision (GR)	Correction of overt grammatical errors (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	(There) the frog jumped
Connector	Repetitive use of conjunctions or time markers at the beginning of utterances (Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy, 2006)	(And then) the frog jumped
Other – “like”	Insertion of the interjection “like”	The frog (like) jumped
Other	Other mazes not defined above	They’re hunters (I guess you could call them)

Mazes were identified by the researcher based on the above criteria and were coded using a color-coding system. The transcripts, sorted by participant code and complete with

color-coded mazes, can be found in Appendix IV: Complete Transcripts. Mazes of each type were then counted for each participant and tabulated (see Appendix V: Maze Coding Counts Tables). The total number of mazes present in that sample were then calculated. This process was completed for all 42 transcripts.

Due to the expected variations observed in the time duration of the picture description tasks and the number of morphemes used, the frequency of each maze-type was converted into a percentage score (see Appendix VI: Maze Percent Scores). This was done by dividing the frequency of each maze-type by the total word count in the sample. The word count would include all words in mazes but not the filled pauses. These tables of percentages were submitted for statistical analyses, the results of which are detailed below.

DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis was completed between the two groups for each of the three linguistic tasks (the Grandfather Passage reading, “Lion and the Rat” picture description task, and “Cookie Theft” picture description task). The two groups of bilinguals were compared based on the percentage of total mazes used, the percentage of total pauses, the percentage of repetitions, and the percentage of revisions. Several repeated measures ANOVAs were performed using the software, Statistica. The between-group variables were bilingual group status (home language of Spanish only vs. home language of both Spanish and English). The within-group variables were types and percentages of mazes. The statistical significance level was set at 0.05.

Reading Task: Grandfather Passage

Analyses of the data revealed that in the reading task (Grandfather Passage), the two bilingual groups did differ in their total percentage of mazes used, $F(1, 6) = 15.23, p = 0.007$. A main effect of group was observed, $F(1, 6) = 6.99, p = 0.038$; the Spanish-only home language group produced a significantly greater percentage of total mazes than the Spanish and English home language group. The types of mazes produced between the two groups for this task also differed significantly, $F(3, 18) = 9.88, p < 0.00$; some maze types (particularly repetitions) were more prevalent than others. Post-hoc testing via Tukey Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) revealed that for the Grandfather Passage task, the Spanish-only home language group produced a greater number of mazes as compared to the Spanish and English home language group. This potentially suggests that a speaker who uses one language at home will produce a higher percentage of mazes than a speaker who uses two languages at home. This difference is very interesting to note because the level of English proficiency across participants was equivalent—all are college students in Orange County who regularly use English in their school and job settings—and therefore the difference cannot be attributed to varying levels of English proficiency. This suggests that a difference in maze use between these two groups can be attributed to their respective home language environments. These results suggest that, at least for this population of study, a bilingual home environment is advantageous in terms of reducing maze production in the L2.

PDT: Lion and the Rat

Analyses of the data revealed that in the “Lion and the Rat” picture description task, the two bilingual groups did not differ significantly in their total percentage of mazes used, $F(1, 6) = 2.73, p = 0.15$. A main effect, however, was observed in terms of types of mazes

produced between the two groups, $F(3, 18) = 86.92, p < 0.00$; some maze types were more prevalent than others. Post-hoc testing using Tukey's HSD method identified that the percentage of total pauses was significantly greater than the percentage of total repetitions as well as total revisions. It also found that the percentage of total repetitions did not differ significantly from the percentage of total revisions.

PDT: Cookie Theft

Analyses of the data found that in the "Cookie Theft" picture description task, there was no significant group effect, $F(1, 6) = 4.89, p = 0.07$; the Spanish-only home language group did not perform significantly differently than the Spanish and English home language in terms of the maze characteristics used. However, there was a main effect of maze type, $F(3, 18) = 49.70, p < 0.00$; some types of mazes were more prevalent than others. A post-hoc analysis using Tukey's HSD method found that the percentage of total pauses was significantly greater than the percentage of total repetitions as well as the percentage of total revisions. Just as was the case in "Lion and the Rat", the percentage of total repetitions did not differ significantly from the percentage of total revisions.

DISCUSSION

Overall, these results suggest a potential advantage of the bilingual home language environment, at least for the population of study. Although groups were similar in their language development, as determined by their case history, there was still a discernable difference between the performance of the Spanish-only home language speakers and the Spanish and English home language speakers. This could potentially suggest that the home

language environment can exert some influence on a bilingual speaker's total percentage of maze production—providing evidence to support this study's hypothesis.

An interesting finding was that the task that was most sensitive to catching differences in performance between the two bilingual groups was the reading passage. This was surprising because as compared to the picture description task, which relies on spontaneous language production and thus creates a higher likelihood of creating errors, the reading passage requires a markedly lower cognitive load, as it does not require any type of improvisation. Because of its simpler nature, it would be expected that the reading passage would yield fewer mazes across groups; and, as such, any potential difference between groups would be minimal, at worst. Conversely, it would be expected that the picture description tasks would yield a greater amount of maze types and frequencies across groups and, as such, there would be more opportunity for significant differences between the groups.

Another finding of note was that the types of mazes produced were sensitive to the task being performed. For instance, in both picture description tasks, the percentage of total pauses was significantly greater than the percentage of total repetitions as well as the percentage of total revisions. Additionally, in both tasks, the percentage of total repetitions and total revisions were not discernable from each other. Thus, specific maze types are also not uniformly distributed.

It is important to note that findings from this study reflect only the specific population of study.

Additionally, it is worth noting that while groups were created based on their reported home language, and that within each group the language development and case history were equivalent, there were two exceptions within the Spanish and English home

language group. While 5 of the 7 participants reported an equilibrated use of both English and Spanish when asked about the language that they used at home with their family, 2 participants reported an unequilibrated use of Spanish and English at home. Participant MM1_HLSE reported that she speaks “both English and Spanish to [her] family, but mostly Spanish with the elderly in [her] family”. This participant was included among the HLSE group because she reported use of both languages at home; however, the frequency at which she utilizes Spanish at home is greater than the frequency at which she uses English at home, because she has more Spanish-speaking communication partners in her home environment. Even so, her performance in percent total mazes, pauses, repetitions, and revisions across all three tasks were unremarkable in comparison with the rest of the HLSE group. The only instance in which she demonstrated a maze characteristics variant from the rest of the HLSE group was in her production of connectors. This participant produced the second-highest percentage of total connectors in the “Lion and the Rat” picture description task, and the third-highest percentage of total connectors in the “Cookie Theft” picture description task. These findings suggest that although this participant did demonstrate an inequivalent use of Spanish and English at home, her results did not starkly vary from the norms within her group. The only potential variation of note was her slightly higher use of connectors. The other participant who demonstrated within-group variation in terms of their language case history was LB_HLSE. Conversely to MM1_HLSE, when asked about the language she uses at home with her family, this participant reported that she uses “English mainly, Spanish occasionally”. This also indicates an unequilibrated use of the two languages. However, as was the case with the aforementioned participant, participant LB_HLSE did not demonstrate a remarkable difference in her percent use of mazes in total mazes, pauses, repetitions, or revisions across all three tasks; that is, her results were

comparable with the performance of the rest of the HLSE group. Once again, the only slightly variant area was in her slightly heightened use of connectors. This participant demonstrated the second-highest percent use of connectors in the “Lion and the Rat” picture description task, and third-highest percent use of connectors in the “Cookie Theft” picture description task.

Thus, as can be seen via the performance of these two participants who slightly varied in their language case history—specifically in the reported frequency at which they use each language at home—this slight in-group variation did not produce a significant difference in their maze frequency or characteristics. The only variation, however small, that was attributed to this in-group difference was a minimally heightened use of connectors in the picture description task. In future studies, it would be advisable to attempt to control for approximately equilibrated language use for bilingual speakers; however, as we have seen in this particular study, the effect appears to be minimal.

At this juncture, it is worth noting that bilingualism itself is a very diverse and broad categorization. Previous studies have shown that particularly within this geographic area of Orange County, bilinguals themselves carry differing levels of bilingualism, as well as differing perceptions as to what exactly constitutes bilingualism. This is typically a product of an individual’s own intersectional sociocultural identities (De La Cruz y Finley, 2021). As such, it becomes difficult for a researcher to empirically define what constitutes “bilingualism”, and even more so to control for participants’ level of bilingualism. This was particularly a challenge when screening out participants to participate in this study. Although there were originally 35 participants for whom data was collected, many had to be screened out due to failure to submit a complete language case history, as well as failure to return for this phase of data collection for the purposes of this project (as was mentioned

earlier, this study was conducted as part of a larger study. The participants from the larger study were invited to return on a second day to partake in this study.). As such, when provided with a smaller sample size of participants, it became necessary to allow for slight variation within the HLSE group—specifically, in the unequilibrated use of Spanish and English among participant MM1_HLSE and LB_HLSE.

Another interesting characteristic of this study's participants is the role that gender played, particularly among groups. Three of the seven Spanish-only home language participants identified as males and the remaining four identified as females. Within the Spanish and English home language group, 7 out of 7 of the participants identified as females—that is, none of the HLSE participants identified as male. This is an interesting phenomenon because it appears to run in accordance with historical sociolinguistic patterns, which observe that females are more prone to language assimilation and driving linguistic change within their communication groups (Labov, 1972). Díaz-Campos explains that one explanation for this phenomenon is that women play a significant role in the formation and development, including language development, of future generations (Díaz-Campos, 36). Additionally, previous studies have demonstrated what is called “la paradoja en el comportamiento lingüístico de las mujeres en cuanto a ser conservadoras y favorecer el uso de variantes consideradas normativas, por una parte, y, por la otra, favorecer el uso de variantes nuevas que poseen prestigio sociolingüístico en la comunidad en que se desarrollan” (40). This phenomenon could serve as a potential explanation for the uneven distribution of gender in the participants. Females are more subject to adopt sociocultural and sociolinguistic norms and are thus more prone to adopting the dominant language in their sphere. This could explain why more females use English, the dominant language in Orange County, even within their home settings—whereas those who identify as males may

be more resistant to this linguistic change, and thus are more prone to retaining solely the use of their native language in the home setting.

It is also worth noting that in previous studies regarding bilingualism, particularly as pertains to maze use, bilingual performance has traditionally been compared to monolingual production. For the purposes of this project, maze production was not compared to monolingual production, but rather focused on within-group analysis between two subsets of bilinguals (based on their home language). This was done intentionally, in order to provide evidence that the comparison of bilinguals to the standards of monolingual norms is a narrow-minded view, and that other levels of analysis among bilingual individuals can prove to be more fruitful.

Significance

This study provides evidence to support the hypothesis that those who utilize their L2 in the home setting demonstrate less mazes—and, by extension, demonstrate less overt cognitive-linguistic demands. This can be attributed to greater exposure and verbal practice in their L2. It can thus be derived that individuals who seek to gain a greater level of verbal proficiency in their L2 would benefit from generalizing their use of the L2 into their home language setting. Home language does appear to have an effect on bilinguals' maze production, at least within the scope of reading from a written stimulus.

At the same time, maze production was not found to completely conform to expectations. For instance, although it was expected that the picture description task would elicit a greater difference in maze production between groups, it was actually the reading passage which was more sensitive to catching this difference. Additionally, there was a heightened use of connectors among the Spanish and English home language group. This

was the only instance in which the HLSE group demonstrated greater maze use as compared to the HLS group.

As such, both mazes and bilingualism proved to be more deeply nuanced than previously thought. The very existence of variation within a single language group (i.e., Spanish-English bilinguals) indicates that there are different factors—such as home language—which contribute to levels of bilingualism and performance in the L2. Bilingualism, then, must not be considered in a monolithic manner. In the realm of education, for example, bilingual students should not be assessed or expected to perform exactly as their bilingual peers. As this study has shown, in-group variation is very common, and should be met with anticipation and an individualized approach.

Finally, the sociocultural relevance of this type of study cannot be stated enough. Within the Spanish-speaking community in Orange County, Hispanic/Latino individuals comprise the overwhelming majority. According to a report from 2019, 25.6% of the Orange County population were reported as native speakers of Spanish, and 32.2% of the population identified as Hispanic or Latino (Data USA). All of the Spanish-speaking participants in this study identified as Hispanic or Latino as well. In a sociocultural sense, there are a multitude of reasons that account for differing levels of retention between Spanish-English bilingual speakers in Orange County. Author Julissa Arce explains that while some families will pass on Spanish to their children, “many Latinos have lost the language for fear of continued oppression”, because they do not want their children to face the same discrimination that they faced for speaking Spanish and for the resulting accent it created (Arce, 2021, p. 74). Still another reason contributing to varying levels of retention of Spanish among the Hispanic/Latino community is the pervasive misinformation regarding bilingualism, especially among educators. An alarming number of educators and

speech-language pathologists misguidedly warn bilingual, largely immigrant, parents to only speak to their child in English at home, for fear of confusing their language development. Despite these practitioners' best intentions, "even if it is unintentional by practitioners or intentionally-on-accident through design of a homogeneous profession, English-only speech therapy demonstrates linguistic oppression, systemic and institutional ableism (the discrimination and social prejudice against disabled people) and raciolinguistic oppression disabled children of color lose their heritage language" (Tisi, 2021). This is the dismal reality that many bilingual families face.

All of this being said, the linear, binary societal viewpoint is simply not representative of the diverse, intersectional reality. This holds true for both society and the present study. Mazes are simultaneously interplaying in a complex manner, even among bilinguals with typically developing speech and language. This underscores the need for a culturally and linguistically responsive outlook to the education and speech-language pathology professions—especially when working with individuals whose L1 is a language other than English.

Limitations & future studies

As mentioned earlier, this study was limited in quantity of eligible participants who met the necessary language case history criteria; and, as such, there was minimal in-group variation for the HLSE group. In future studies, it would be interesting to see whether the inherent variation within the HLSE group influences the outcome of maze production.

This study was limited in that only English linguistic data was collected. The presentation of stimuli was in English, the tasks were in English, and the response modality was verbally produced English. In a future study, it would be important to include the

impact that home language has on Spanish production. In this case, it would be hypothesized that those who use only Spanish at home would produce fewer mazes in Spanish, as compared to the Spanish and English home language group. Bilingual studies, to be maximally valid, must include data collection for both languages. Unfortunately, in this study, the researcher was limited to data from only one language.

Another limitation of this study was in the maze-tabulating process. Although the researcher coded mazes in concordance with the definitions set by Bedore, Fiestas, Peña, and Nagy (2006), it was inevitable that some degree of human error was involved. With each transcription, the researcher gained a better understanding of how examples of maze manifest in actual speech production. After all transcripts were coded, the researcher returned to the first transcripts to re-analyze them, this time with a better understanding of what different maze types would manifest. Even so, it is likely that there were some discrepancies in how some mazes were coded. For future studies, the use of a standardized software such as the Systematic Analysis of Language Transcripts (SALT) would prove invaluable in ensuring that mazes were codified in a consistent fashion across all transcripts. This would subsequently ensure inter-group transcriber reliability.

In future studies, it would be interesting to explore the influence of code-switching on maze use. Because studies related to maze and bilingualism are already limited, there are even fewer related to code-switching. It would be interesting to see the degree to which types of mazes produced by bilinguals are manifestations of code-switching.

Future studies should also seek to find more culturally relevant picture description task stimuli in order to elicit the most amount of meaningful language. The “Cookie Theft” picture description task is taken from 2001 and depicts a scene that may not be experientially relevant to many individuals. As Dr. Seles Gadsons explains, “picture

description tasks that do not include semantic experiences that are relevant to the client decrease the use of available language” (Seles Gadson). As such, it would be advisable for not only future studies, but also in clinical practice, to use culturally relevant and meaningful picture description stimuli. This would remove a confounding variable that is related to limited experiential language to describe the task.

Future directions should also involve a deeper analysis based on specific types of mazes. For the purposes of this study, only the percentage of total mazes, total pauses, total repetitions, and total revisions were explored; however, there remains the opportunity to explore the types of pauses (empty versus filled), for example, more deeply. Additionally, it would be beneficial to compare how one group performs on each of the three different tasks. This analysis focused on comparing the two groups for each of the three tasks; however, it did not explore how, for example, the HLS group compared in performance in the reading passage versus in the “Cookie Theft” versus the “Lion and the Rat” picture description tasks.

Clearly, more participants are needed to understand the intricacies and the power of the observed production patterns in this specific linguistic group.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank Dr. Rahul Chakraborty for his research support throughout the process of brainstorming, revising, statistically analyzing, and producing this final project. I also thank Dr. Minjung Kim, Dr. André Zampaulo, Dr. Toya Wyatt, and Dr. Reyes Fidalgo for their support in developing my research questions. Thank you to the student organization, STANCE, for igniting my passion for social and linguistic justice within the

field of speech-language pathology. Thank you to my friends and family who supported me throughout this journey via lengthy discussions, conference presentations, moral support, and encouraging me to realize my best self. Y gracias a mi querido abuelito y mis queridas abuelitas, por su amor, sus sacrificios, y por mostrarme la gran belleza de mis raíces. Dedico mis logros a ustedes. Finalmente, doy las gracias a Dios, por quien todo ha sido posible.

REFERENCES

- Arce Raya, J.N. (2022). *You Sound Like a White Girl: The case for rejecting assimilation*. Flatiron Books.
- Byrd, C. T., Bedore, L. M., & Ramos, D. (2015). The Disfluent Speech of Bilingual Spanish–English Children: Considerations for Differential Diagnosis of Stuttering. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 46*(1), 30–43.
https://doi.org/10.1044/2014_LSHSS-14-0010
- Chakraborty, R., Domsch, C., & Gonzales, D. (2011, November). Influence of L2 Proficiency on Maze Use. Poster presented at the annual convention of the American Speech & Hearing Association, San Diego, California.
- Chakraborty, R., Kim, Minjung, Trevino, C., **De La Cruz, R.**, & Moss, S. (2021, November). Influence of L1 on Frequency and Types of Mazes in L2 Early Bilinguals. Poster presented at the annual convention of the American Speech & Hearing Association, Washington, D.C.
- Chakraborty, R., Morales, N., Fritsch, K., & Gonzales, M. D. (2017). Second Language Proficiency and Maze: Marathi-English Bilinguals. *Clinical Archives of Communication Disorders, 2*(2), 103–115.
<https://doi.org/10.21849/cacd.2017.00101>
- Data USA (2019). “Orange County, CA.” *Deloitte*. <https://datausa.io/profile/geo/orange-county-ca>
- De La Cruz, R.** & Finley, I. (in press). The Impact of Globalized Spanish on American Sociocultural Attitudes. *Actas del Séptimo Congreso Internacional Latinoamérica: Tradición y globalización en el siglo XXI*, Universidad Internacional en Cuernavaca.

Díaz-Campos, M. (2011). Introduction. En *The handbook of Hispanic sociolinguistics*, pp. 1-5. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.

Díaz-Campos, M. (2014). *Introducción a la sociolingüística hispánica*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Discriminación por Idioma: Sus derechos legales. *The Legal Aid Society of San Francisco Employment Law Center*.

Eckert, P. (1990). Cooperative competition in adolescent “girl talk”. *Discourse Processes*, 13, 91-122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01638539009544748>

Enríquez, N. (2020). *Pausas y actividad neuronal en la producción oral de hablantes de herencia, nativos y no nativos de español e inglés utilizando electroencefalograma* (Publication No. 28181194). [Doctoral dissertation, University of Houston].

ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.

Fiestas, C., Peña, E., & Nagy, V. (2006). Cross-language comparisons of maze use in Spanish and English in functionally monolingual and bilingual children.

Bilingualism: Language and Cognition, 9, 233–247.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728906002604>

Goodglass, H., Kaplan, E., & Barresi, B (2001). *Boston Diagnostic Aphasia Examination Third Edition (BDAE-3)*. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

<https://www.proedinc.com/Products/11850/bdae3-boston-diagnostic-aphasia-examinationthird-edition.aspx>

Guo, L., Tomblin, J. B., & Samelson, V. (2008). Speech Disruptions in the Narratives of English-Speaking Children with Specific Language Impairment. *Journal of Speech*,

Language, and Hearing Research, 51(3), 722–738. [https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388\(2008/051\)](https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388(2008/051))

Labov, W. (1972). *Sociolinguistic patterns*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania press.

Labov, W. (2001). *Principles of linguistic change, internal factors*. Oxford: Blackwell.

Leadolm, B., & Miller, J. (1994). *Language Sample Analysis: The Wisconsin Guide*.

Wisconsin State Department of Public Instruction, Madison.

Leonard, J. (2004). *Bilingualism and Equality: Title VII Claims for Language*

Discrimination in the Workplace. 38, 85.

Leonard, J. (2007). Title VII and the Protection of Minority Languages in the American

Workplace: The Search for a Justification. *Missouri Law Review*, 72, 49.

Loban, W. (1976). *Language development: Kindergarten through grade twelve*. Urbana,

IL: National Council of Teachers of English.

Matsuda, M. J. (1991). Voices of America: Accent, Antidiscrimination Law, and a

Jurisprudence for the Last Reconstruction. *The Yale Law Journal*, 100(5), 1329.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/796694>

“Mazes and Abandoned Utterances: Why they Matter.” *SALT Software*, 2021.

<https://www.saltsoftware.com/blog/mazes-abandoned-utterances>

Nettelbladt, U., & Hansson, K. (1999). Mazes in Swedish pre-school children with specific

language impairment. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 13(6), 483-

497. <https://doi.org/10.1080/026992099298997>

Pinkney, J. Aesop’s fables. Chronicle Books. 2000.

Reilly, J., & Fisher, J. L. (2012). Sherlock Holmes and the Strange Case of the Missing

Attribution: A Historical Note on “The Grandfather Passage.” *Journal of Speech*,

Language, and Hearing Research, 55(1), 84–88. [https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388\(2011/11-0158\)](https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388(2011/11-0158))

Ribot, K. M., & Hoff, E. (2014). “¿Cómo estas?” “I’m good.” Conversational code-switching is related to profiles of expressive and receptive proficiency in Spanish-English bilingual toddlers. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 38(4), 333–341. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025414533225>

SALT Software (2021). *Transcription Conventions: Standard Salt Conventions*. SALT Software, LLC.
<https://www.saltsoftware.com/pub/media/wysiwyg/tran aids/StandardConventions.pdf>

Seles Gadson, D. [@dseles_phd]. (2022, May 15). “Stop asking Black people to describe pictures that don’t look like them.” Retrieved from Instagram.

Taliancich-Klinger, C. L., & Bedore, L. M. (2019). Frequency of mazes in an experimental narrative task in monolingual English and Spanish-English bilingual children. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 33(6), 547–569.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02699206.2018.1563215>

Tisi, V. & Sheen Chiou, H. “Raciolinguistic Oppression of Pacific Islanders and Asians and the Role of Advocacy within the field of Speech-Language Pathology.’ 20 Jun. 2021. <https://speechologist.medium.com/linguistic-and-race-advocacy-for-pacific-islanders-and-asians-within-the-field-of-speech-language-405d3564e54e>

Valles, J. (2016). *The Spanish-English Bilingual: A Cross-Classification Comparison of Maze Use in Children*. 64.

Appendix I: Promotional Flyer

Speech and language characteristics of bilingual adults with variable linguistic experience

We are looking for monolingual and bilingual adult speakers (i.e., monolingual English, bilingual Korean-English, bilingual Spanish-English, bilingual Mandarin-English, bilingual Vietnamese-English, and bilingual Hindi-English speakers) to participate in a study. You must also be a current CSUF student to participate. This study examines the influence of linguistic experience (various first language background) on production behaviors. Data will be collected in the Bilingualism and Speech Production Laboratory in the Speech and Hearing Clinic (CP-150) at CSUF. This project will require about 2 hours of participation. Therefore, if you choose to participate, you will be compensated with an incentive of \$40 for your participation.

You may be eligible for this study if your primary language is English, you are 18 years old or older, and you are:

- a monolingual English speaker
- or
- a bilingual Korean-English speaker
- or
- a bilingual Spanish-English speaker
- or
- a bilingual Mandarin-English speaker
- or
- a bilingual Vietnamese-English speaker
- or
- a bilingual Hindi-English speaker

If you are interested in participating in this study, please contact:

Student research assistants

Department of Communication Sciences and Disorders

email: bilingualspeechproject@gmail.com

Appendix II: Language Case History

1. Were you born and brought up in the USA?
2. If you were not born in this country, when did you arrive here in the USA?
3. Is English your primary language?
4. Age of initial exposure to the English language?
5. Do you know any other language or languages besides English (if yes, please indicate what other languages you know)?
6. How many hours within a day do you use your other language or languages either for speaking or writing?
7. In your family, what language do you use to interact with your family members?
8. Do either of your parents speak a different language at home?
9. Are you able to return for a second session that will take approximately 30 minutes?
10. Sex (M/F)

Appendix III: Testing Stimuli*Grandfather Passage***Grandfather Passage**

You wish to know all about my grandfather. Well, he is nearly 93 years old, yet he still thinks as swiftly as ever. He dresses himself in an old black frock coat, usually several buttons missing. A long beard clings to his chin, giving those who observe him a pronounced feeling of the utmost respect. When he speaks, his voice is just a bit cracked and quivers a bit. Twice each day he plays skillfully and with zest upon a small organ. Except in the winter when the snow or ice prevents, he slowly takes a short walk in the open air each day. We have often urged him to walk more and smoke less, but he always answers, "Banana oil!" Grandfather likes to be modern in his language.

Lion and the Rat

Cookie Theft

Copyright © 1983 by Lee & Fetzer

Appendix IV: Complete Transcripts

The complete transcripts with maze coding for all 14 participants can be found at this link:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/3fxnycwd89okinw/Complete%20Transcripts%20-%20GP_Rat_Cookie.pdf?dl=0

Appendix V: Maze Coding Counts Tables

Maze Counts: Grandfather Passage

	GP MAZE ANALYSIS											
CODE	Empty Pause	FILLED PAUSE	Sound Rep	Part Word Rep	Whole Word Rep	Phrase Rep	Phon Rev	Lex Rev	Gram Rev	Conn	Other - "like"	Other
NS1_HLS	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
JA2_HLS	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
MM2_HLS	0	3	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
LL1_HLS	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0
JS5_HLS	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
WB_HLS	1	0	2	0	1	4	1	0	1	0	0	0
BA_HLS	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MM1_HLS>E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SP1_HLSE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RV_HLSE	0	0	2	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
EC_HLSE	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
JS2_HLSE	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ED1_HLSE	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
LB_HLE>S	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Maze Counts: Rat

PDT MAZE ANALYSIS: RAT												
CODE	Empty Pause	FILLED PAUSE	Sound Rep	Part Word Rep	Whole Word Rep	Phrase Rep	Phon Rev	Lex Rev	Gram Rev	Conn	Other - "like"	Other
NS1_HLS	1	4	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	10	3	1
JA2_HLS	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	1	0
MM2_HLS	0	6	1	1	0	0	0	6	0	1	3	3
LL1_HLS	15	15	0	1	2	3	1	2	0	1	0	0
JS5_HLS	0	17	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	8	3	3
WB_HLS	2	15	0	0	3	4	0	1	0	0	1	3
BA_HLS	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	2	0	3
MM1_HLS>E	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0
SP1_HLSE	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
RV_HLSE	3	8	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	0	1
EC_HLSE	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	6	1	2	0	0
JS2_HLSE	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	9	0	2
ED1_HLSE	0	7	0	0	1	0	0	4	0	2	0	2
LB_HLE>S	2	8	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	8	1	1

Maze Counts: Cookie

PDT MAZE ANALYSIS: COOKIE											
CODE	Empty Pause	FILLED PAUSE	Sound Rep	Part Word Rep	Whole Word Rep	Phrase Rep	Phon Rev	Lex Rev	Gram Rev	Connector	Other - "like"
NS1_HLS	4	6	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	9	1
JA2_HLS	0	7	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
MM2_HLS	0	7	2	0	0	0	1	3	2	1	0
LL1_HLS	7	12	1	0	2	0	0	5	0	0	1
JS5_HLS	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
WB_HLS	0	24	2	0	6	1	0	5	0	0	4
BA_HLS	0	13	3	0	3	1	0	0	0	6	0
MM1_HLS>E	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	0
SP1_HLSE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RV_HLSE	1	9	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0
EC_HLSE	1	8	1	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	1
JS2_HLSE	1	12	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	18	7
ED1_HLSE	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	0
LB_HLE>S	4	15	0	0	3	0	0	2	0	6	1

Appendix VI: Maze Percent Scores

The complete set of tables with percentage scores for each maze type for each participant in each group can be found at this link:

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/goc7jyk0eb5ud79/SHP%20-%20All%20Maze%20Analysis%20statistics.xlsx?dl=0>

